

RESEARCH OF STUDENTS' PSYCHOLOGICAL STATE AND HAPPINESS INDICATORS IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS AS AN IMPORTANT FACTOR IN MANAGEMENT OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

In the effective management of education, the psychological features of focusing on the psychological characteristics of students and taking into account the level of family happiness are highlighted in this article. experimental results of negative correlation are given.

We know that psychological characteristics in people have a negative or positive effect on their quality of life. In order to study this process, we analyzed the influence of aggressiveness and hostility on the feeling of family happiness or lack of happiness in students. For this, we used the scale "Diagnostics of Hostility and Enmity" by U. Cook and D. Medlane, adapted by L. N. Sobchik. The results obtained are presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1.

The effect of aggression and hostility on the feeling of family happiness or lack of happiness in students (n=340)

№	Class	Scales	Feeling family happiness		Inability to feel family happiness	
			Boy	Girl	Boy	Girl
1	Teenagers (n=136)	Aggressiveness	0,272*	-0,113	0,159	0,139
		Feeling of hostility	0,271*	-0,259*	0,333**	-0,103
2	Maturity period (n=169)	Aggressiveness	0,211	0,263**	0,311**	0,332**
		Feeling of hostility	-	-	-	0,011
			0,347**	0,155	0,188	

Note: * p≤0,05; ** p≤0,01.

According to the results obtained, the feeling of family happiness in adolescent boys is significantly correlated with the level of aggression ($r=0.272$; $p\leq 0.05$), hostility ($r=0.271$; $p\leq 0.05$), hostility in girls ($r=-0.259$; $p\leq 0.05$), and the lack of feeling family happiness is significantly correlated with hostility ($r=0.333$; $p\leq 0.01$). In adult boys, the feeling of family happiness is significantly correlated with hostility ($r=-0.347$; $p\leq 0.01$), aggression in girls ($r=0.263$; $p\leq 0.01$), and the lack of feeling family happiness is significantly correlated with aggression in boys ($r=0.311$; $p\leq 0.01$), and aggression in girls ($r=0.332$; $p\leq 0.01$). It is interesting that the criterion of feeling family happiness was found to be positively correlated with aggression and hostility in adolescent boys and with aggression in adult girls. As we know, aggression is a relatively stable personality trait that expresses aggression, that is, readiness to harm others, as well as a tendency to accept and understand the behavior and actions of others on the basis of hostility [1]. From the results of the above experiment, we can see that negative psychological traits, such as aggression and hostility, cause students to not feel happiness. Thus, they manifest their negative characteristics in the educational process. This causes inadequacy of the internal rules, systems, and established norms established in the educational process. How do these negative psychological traits affect the components we are studying? In order to analyze the behavior of Keeling, we will consider each of them separately below. Hostility is an unpleasant, angry, spiteful, vindictive, and vindictive form of behavior[1]. Aggression is a personal trait expressed in actions and behaviors aimed at harming others or oneself. Hostility is manifested by physical harm, insults. Aggressive people are irritable, touchy. Diagnosis is carried out by clinical methods, using psychodiagnostic questionnaires of the individual, projective tests. To reduce aggression, psychoanalysis, cognitive-behavioral psychotherapy, auto-training, and correction with medications are used[2].

Continuing education is a holistic educational system consisting of logically interconnected and mutually dependent stages, developing from simple to complex. The basis of the personnel training system in the Republic of Uzbekistan is one of the main principles of state policy in the field of education. It is enshrined as a separate principle in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" adopted on August 29, 1997 and the National Program for Personnel Training. Continuing education is one of the main structural components of the national model (see National model of education), a priority area that ensures the socio-economic development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, meets the economic, social, scientific-technical and cultural needs of the individual, society and the state. Continuing education creates the necessary conditions for the formation of a creative, socially active, spiritually rich personality and the training of highly qualified competitive personnel. The functioning of the continuous education system is ensured on the basis of state educational standards, the consistency of educational programs at different levels and includes preschool education, general secondary education, secondary specialized, vocational education, higher education, post-secondary education, advanced training and retraining of personnel, and extracurricular education[3]. We have become familiar with the definitions of the components we are studying. Negative psychological characteristics do not allow individuals to feel psychological well-being, the psychological characteristics of such students are prone to resistance to accepting new things, taking new approaches, creating, and following discipline. It is clear that

the effective management of the educational process consisting of such students causes a number of difficulties.

In conclusion, we would like to say that in order to continuously and effectively manage the educational process, psychological well-being must be a requirement. It is appropriate to study a number of factors that create this well-being, dwell on them in detail, and reveal their psychological characteristics..

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